

A novel locality-based clustering method of undirected, unweighted networks

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Abstract

In this paper a new locality-based clustering algorithm is introduced for partitioning undirected, unweighted graphs. This algorithm applies a new similarity measure based on the common neighbors of the vertices. Results of the suggested algorithm are compared to the generated clusters of the Girvan-Newman method as well as the running time is also measured on different data sets. The efficiency and the advantages of the proposed method, as well as our results are also presented in this paper through some application examples.

Keywords: graphmining, clustering, unweighted network

Introduction

Real world objects, such as people, web pages, molecules, emails or companies are connected with each other via internet links, friendships or economic relations. This way, objects and their relationships can be thought as a network in which vertices correspond to the objects and the edges represent relationships between them. Questions "What communities can be explored in a networks of objects?" or "How can be these communities detected?" formulate the basic problem of several applied research and social network analysis.

The objects determined by their real life properties and the links connect them form communities in various sizes and shapes. Communities (Newman, 2003) mean such groups of objects where objects in the same group are connected with many links to each other, but we can find relatively few edges between objects placed in different groups. More formally, the analyzed objects and the relationships between them can be seen as a graph, and graph clustering aims to separate sparsely connected dense subgraphs from each other. The

problem of finding good division of networks has been studied in various application areas for example analyzing social networks (Wasserman, 1994), web graphs (Virtanen, 2003), or biological structures (King, 2004).

In the simplest case the analyzed network is an unweighted and undirected graph. It means that the relationships do not have orientation and the intensity of the relationships is not known or it is not significant. In this case the network of the objects presents only the existence of the relationships between the objects to be analyzed. If two objects are connected with each other in the real world, nodes corresponding to these objects are also connected in the graph, but in any other cases nodes are not linked to each other. Therefore, the structural construction of the network is the only information which may help the analyzers to identify the well separated groups.

There exist several methods to identify well separated groups of the objects in the networks, such as Girvan-Newman algorithm (Girvan, 2002), minimum-cut method (Saha, 2007), clique based methods (Derényi, 2005; Palla et al., 2005), or the Markov Clustering Algorithm (van Dongen, 2000). These methods differ considerably from each other, as they define the concept of well separated clusters in various forms and they utilize different approaches to identify them.

In this paper we propose a new graph clustering method that identifies the group of the elements based on the local environment of the objects. Graph clustering approaches presented in the literatures can be seen mainly as global clustering methods as they try to find the communities of the objects in such a way, that they take the whole structure of the objects into account. In our approach only the local environment of the objects is taken into account, and farther objects are neglected. The basic idea of the suggested similarity measure is, that objects belonging to the same cluster share more common neighbors, than objects belonging to different clusters. In our method a new similarity measure is assigned to each vertex based on the number of the common neighbors of the objects connected. The suggested similarity measure can be calculated in various range of the objects and hereby the spreading of the local environment is pliable. Based on this principle we propose a hierarchical graph clustering method that identifies the communities based on this new similarity measure. The proposed method shows good performance in the identification of communities of objects placed on the margin, and it is able to detect clusters of different shapes and sizes.

To introduce the efficiency of the proposed method we present four application examples, containing synthetic data set and real life networks as well. In these examples the Girvan-Newman method and our method are compared with each other. The efficiency of the examined methods is presented with the measuring the clustering rate and evaluating the running time.

The remaining part of this paper is organized as follows. The section “Theoretical background” introduces the main notions and concepts of graph clustering, section “Common neighbors based graph clustering method” presents our new graph clustering approach, section “Application examples” shows the efficiency of the presented method through some application examples, and “Conclusion” summarizes the main benefits and results of the proposed method.

Theoretical background

Cluster analysis as a main task of data mining aims to classify the objects into well separated clusters. Well separated means that objects placed in the same cluster are very similar, whereas objects belonging to different clusters are as dissimilar as possible. Usually, objects are characterized with many attributes and they can be thought as n -dimensional objects in the n -dimensional vector space. Clustering aims to group these data points into clusters based on their distances from each other. Graph clustering is a special area of clustering, where objects are determined not only by its attributes, but also their relationships are relevant. In such a clustering problems not the distances of the objects are substantial, but the structural construction of the network.

Formally, let the number of the objects N , and denote V_1, V_2, \dots, V_N the objects to be analyzed. If there exists a relationship between objects V_i, V_j , connect them with an edge e_{ij} . So the whole structure of the objects can be described as a graph $G=(V,E)$, where $V=\{ V_1, V_2, \dots, V_N \}$, and E is the set of the edges. A graph is undirected if the edges have no orientation, and a graph is unweighted if no weight is associated to the edges. That means, in unweighted graphs only the existence of the relationship is presented, but the strength of the relations are not known. An unweighted, undirected graph may represent for example a group of people, where nodes represent the individual persons and edges represent relations (e.g. acquaintance) that exist between two members of the group.

There are several graph clustering methods to detect communities in unweighted, undirected networks. One of the most commonly used methods is the Girvan-Newman method (Girvan, 2002). The Girvan-Newman algorithm is a hierarchical graph clustering method, which iteratively identifies and removes edges lying between the communities. The identification of edges to be removed is based on the measure “edge betweenness” proposed by Girvan and Newman. Edge betweenness is a similar concept to the Freeman’s centrality measure betweenness (Freeman, 1977). The measure of edge betweenness of an edge is equal to the number of shortest paths from all vertices to all others that pass through that edge. The main idea of this clustering approach is that those edges that connect different groups have high edge betweenness measure, because all shortest paths between different communities must go along one of these inter-group edges. The algorithm repeatedly identifies edges with the highest edge betweenness measure and removes them. In each iteration step first it computes the edge betweenness for all edges in the network, than it removes the edge with the highest edge betweenness measure and finally it recalculates the edge betweenness for all remained edges. The repeated recalculation of the measure edge betweenness for all edges gives the main drawback of this method. Although the Girvan-Newman works well on unweighted, undirected networks, the computational cost in case of large networks is very significant.

K -clique methods are widely studied and applied graph clustering methods in practical social network analysis (e.g. Palla et al., 2005; Palla et al., 2007). Cliques in undirected graphs are such subgraphs in which every two vertices are connected by an edge. K -cliques are fully connected subgraphs with k nodes. The popular clique percolation method (CPM) was proposed by Palla et al. in 2005. In contrast with the hard clustering approaches, this method is able to detect overlapping community structure of networks as well. This method defines communities as maximal union of k -cliques that are connected through adjacent k -cliques. Two k -cliques are considered adjacent if they share $k-1$ nodes. As clique based methods aim to find such adjacent cliques that can be rolled into each other, they can

unfold only such communities in which the members are strongly connected. Furthermore, we have to notice that maximal clique detection is NP-complete (Bomze et al., 1999). There was published different improvement versions of CPM method, for example it was extended to handle directed networks (Directed Clique Percolation Method - CPMd) and weighted networks (Weighted Clique Percolation Method - CPMw) as well, furthermore incremental version was also proposed for dynamic social networks (Duan et al., 2012), too.

The Markov Clustering (MCL) method (van Dongen, 2000) is a fast and scalable unsupervised cluster algorithm for networks. The algorithm simulates random walks in a graph, and it is based on the intuition that a random walk will likely not leave the dense cluster until many of its vertices have been visited. Random walks on a graph are calculated using “Markov Chains”. The MCL algorithm iteratively modifies a matrix of transition probabilities with the following two operations: expansion and inflation. The expansion operator is responsible for allowing flow to connect different regions of the graph, and the inflation operator is responsible for both strengthening and weakening of current. The algorithm repeats these steps until a steady state is reached. The algorithm has $O(N^3)$ complexity, where N is the number of the vertices. It is able to work with weighted and unweighted graphs, robust against noise, and it is not necessary to specify the number of the clusters a priori, but it cannot find overlapping clusters and it is not suitable for clusters with large diameter.

Minimum-cut clustering (MCC) methods (e.g. Saha, 2007) aim to divide the graph into a predetermined number of subgraphs in such a way, that the number of edges between the resulted subgraphs is minimized. In weighted graphs these methods try to maximize the sum of the weights of the edges within the clusters, which is equivalent to minimizing the sum of the weights of the edges that go between clusters. The main drawback of these methods is that they search communities in a predetermined number, and they may force to find such groups which do not exist in the graph evidently. Furthermore, the minimum-cut clustering is an NP-hard problem.

Of course, there exist several other graph clustering methods as well. Some of them are based on edge cutting and/or they try to optimize partition criteria, like conductance or clustering coefficient, while again others work based on spectral methods. Global clustering methods find communities looking at the whole graph, while local methods try to find communities by taking only the local environment of the vertices into account. As local methods look only a few vertices and its connections simultaneously, they may work better in large networks than the main part of the global clustering methods.

Common neighbors based graph clustering method

In this section we introduce our new graph clustering method to detect the communities in unweighted, undirected networks. The proposed method is a hierarchical divisive graph clustering method which iterative identifies and removes edges from the graph. To identify these unnecessary edges we introduce a new similarity measure which is based on the common neighbors of the vertices. Furthermore, the proposed method is a local clustering algorithm. That is to say, to compute the proposed similarity measure, it considers the local neighborhood of the vertices only, hereby it can work efficiently with large networks as well. Contrarily, the Girvan-Newman method can be seen as a global graph clustering algorithm, since to compute the centrality measure of the edges (edge betweenness) it

determines the shortest paths between each pair of vertices, hereby it is impractical for very large graphs.

As we have mentioned, the proposed algorithm is based on the computing of a local similarity measure. The idea to compute this neighborhood measure is arising from the Jarvis-Patrick clustering algorithm (Jarvis, 1973). The Jarvis-Patrick clustering algorithm is a very simple clustering method, which utilizes the neighborhood relations of the objects to disclose the hidden clusters. The algorithm first finds the k nearest neighbors of all objects, and then it places two objects in the same cluster whenever they fulfill the following two conditions: (i) they must be in the set of each other's k -nearest neighbors, and (ii) they must have at least l nearest neighbors in common. Parameters k and l are determined by the user.

In our approach we utilize the idea of common neighbors of the vertices, but the neighborhood relations are given by the network to be analyzed, and we do not have to create the k -nn graph of the objects as it has been shown in the Jarvis-Patrick method. The proposed similarity measure based on the number of the common neighbors can be calculated as follows:

$$w_{i,j} = \left(\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{1}{n_j} \right) (1 + m_{i,j}) \quad (1)$$

where n_i denotes the number of the direct neighbors of vertices V_i , and n_j respectively for V_j . Furthermore, $m_{i,j}$ denotes the number of the common neighbors of vertices V_i and V_j .

The proposed algorithm is based on that assumption that vertices belonging to different communities share only few common neighbors. The algorithm iterative computes this similarity measures for all edges which exist in the graph at the current step and it removes the edge with the smallest similarity measure. The detailed steps of the proposed Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method (CNGC method) are the follows:

- Step 1: Determine the set of the direct neighbors of all vertices.
- Step 2: Calculate the similarity measure presented in Equation(1) for all edges existing in the graph.
- Step 3: Remove the edge from the network with the smallest similarity measure.
- Step 4: Go back to Step 1 until a terminating criterion is not satisfied.

As other hierarchical methods, this approach also requires a terminating condition. The algorithm can stop, if the number of the clusters reaches a predetermined number or the similarity measure becomes greater than a threshold value. Of course, it is not easy to determine the number of the clusters a priori. In order to reach a more accurate clustering of data set, it is a good strategy to choose a greater number for the number of clusters, and after running the algorithm we can examine the facility of the merging some groups together. If during the algorithm vertices belonging to two different groups have been lost only such edges that connect the members of these groups together, we can merge these group.

We have to mention that the repetitive determination of the direct neighbors for all vertices, and the repetitive computation of similarity measure for all edges are partway unnecessary. It is sufficient to determine the set of neighbors of those vertices which were affected in the last iteration and analogously it is sufficient to compute the similarity

measure only for those edges which connects such vertices which were affected in the last iteration step.

Application examples

Our locality-based clustering method was examined using different data sets. In this article we compare our algorithm with the Girvan-Newman method. Running results are presented through 4 application examples. One of them is an artificial data set, and the other three are real life data sets. To measure the performance of the methods we have calculated the clustering rate in all cases. The clustering rate in these cases was calculated as the ratio of the number of the well clustered nodes to the number of all nodes. As in all four cases there can be found an expected clustering result, we have considered them as correct clustering results. Furthermore, we have compared the edge and group cutting time as well in all cases under study.

Girvan (Girvan, 2002) shows a generated simplified schematic representation of a social network with 22 vertices, 37 edges and 3 clusters. The speciality of this data set is that it contains a community in which the neighboring vertices do not share common neighbors. As our method is based on the number of the common neighbors, it looked like interesting to work with this data set. While generated networks provide well-controlled test cases for validating clustering algorithms, it is also expected to test the constructed algorithm on data from real world. Zachary built a network representing friendships between members of a “karate club” (Zachary, 1977). The data was collected from the members of a university karate club by Wayne Zachary in 1977. Each node represents a member of the club, and edges represent different common activities between two members of the club. In this example we have shown the simple unweighted version of his network. After long disputes between two factions of the club, the karate club was split into two separate clubs. So, this data set contains only 2 clusters while the numbers of the vertices and edges are 34 and 78, respectively. Lusseau et al. analyzed the social network of a community of 62 bottlenose dolphins (Lusseau et al., 2003). The network consists of two main groups and the second clusters may split into four subgroups, as well. The whole network includes 62 vertices and 159 edges and it is a more complex structure for testing our algorithm. Finally, a fourth data set is used for validating our clustering solution based on a collaboration network of scientists at the Santa Fe Institute (Girvan, 2002). The published 118 vertices, 198 edges and 7 clusters in this network represent scientists at the Santa Fe Institute and their collaborators between 1999 and 2000.

The results of clustering algorithms of the Girvan-Newman and our locality-based clustering methods are summarized in Table 1. As a result, we have found that both the Girvan-Newman algorithm and our suggested Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method operate without clustering mistakes on the generated network since all the three clusters were detected perfectly in both cases. The clustering results of the ‘Karate club’ are similar in case of both methods. Our Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method had to eliminate 10 edges to unfold the two groups of the members, and it has misclassified only one node, yield by the number 10. The Girvan-Newman method has also only one node (yield by 3) classified incorrectly. To reach this result this algorithm had eliminated 12 edges. So, clustering rates in both cases were 97%. During the tests of the third data set

(Social network of a community of bottlenose dolphins) our aim was to examine how the algorithms find the 5 clusters. To eliminate the 5 clusters the Girvan-Newman algorithm has eliminated 41 edges and it has been resulted in 7 clusters. The Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method has eliminated 50 edges and it has been resulted in 8 clusters. The proposed method has misclassified 3 vertices, and the clustering rate is 95%, which can be considered as a good clustering result. Finally, on the ‘collaboration network of scientists’ data set both methods have been misclassified 3 vertices. While the Girvan-Newman method has separated 9 groups, our suggested method has separated 10 groups. Applying the suggested merging refinement on these subgroups we can get the expected 7 clusters with 1 misclassification error, which means 99% clustering rate in both cases.

The results of clustering algorithms of the Girvan-Newman and our locality-based clustering methods are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of the Girvan-Newman, and the Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering methods

Data set	Method	# of clusters generated by the method	# of wrongly clustered vertices
Synthetic network (Girvan, 2002)	CNGC algorithm	3	0
	Girvan-Newman algorithm	3	0
‘Karate club’ (Zachary, 1977)	CNGC algorithm	2	1
	Girvan-Newman algorithm	2	1
Social network of a community of bottlenose dolphins (Lusseau et al., 2003)	CNGC algorithm	8	3
	Girvan-Newman algorithm	7	0
Collaboration network of scientists (Girvan, 2002)	CNGC algorithm	10	1
	Girvan-Newman algorithm	9	1

Speedtest of the algorithms

During our tests we have compared the average running time of identifying and removing an edge (average time of edge cutting), and the average running time of separating two groups (average group cutting time) for both methods. Our expectation was that the Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method need less time to identify and remove an unnecessary edge and its need less time to separate different communities, than the Girvan-Newman method. Figure 1 shows the average group and edge cutting time of the Girvan-Newman and Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering methods on the four data sets.

(a) Synthetic data set

(b) Zachary's karate club data set

(c) Dolphins data set

(d) Collaboration data set

Figure 1 Average group and edge cutting time of the Girvan-Newman and Common Neighbors based Clustering algorithms on different data sets

As we can see, the Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering method needs more less time both to identify and remove unnecessary edges and to separate different groups. Data show that in general the Girvan-Newman algorithm is slower approximately with one order than our Common Neighbors based Graph Clustering algorithm. The advantage of our method is arising from that fact, that contrary to the Girvan-Newman method, which is a global clustering algorithm, our suggested method is a local clustering algorithm. While the Girvan-Newman method in each iteration step calculates the measure of edge betweenness in such a way, that it have to determine the shortest paths between all pairs of vertices, our suggested method calculates the similarity measures by taking only the local environment of the vertices into account.

Conclusion

In this paper we have presented a new graph clustering method which is suitable for identifying community structures in unweighted, undirected networks. The algorithm is a hierarchical divisive method which iterative identifies and removes edges from the graph connecting the different clusters together. The efficiency of the proposed method was demonstrated trough synthetic and real life application examples. These examples show that the proposed method serves good clustering results in the analyzed cases, and it is specifically efficient to identify clusters lying on the periphery on the analyzed network. Furthermore, we have compared the running time of the algorithm presented in this paper with a popular clustering method, namely the Girvan-Newman algorithm. As our new method is a local clustering algorithm, we have observed, that the running time of the proposed method is much more less than the Girvan-Newman method, which is a global graph clustering method.

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